

Computational Analysis of Binomial Series and Binomial Coefficients

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper discusses the computational analysis of binomial series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, binomial coefficient, binomial series, combinatorics

1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-9]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-9] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series [10-19]. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

3. Computational Analysis of Binomial Series

We know that the general binomial series is $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^i y^{n-i} = (x+y)^n$.

Theorem 3.1: $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^i (1-x)^{n-i} = 1$.

Proof. Let us substitute $y = 1-x$ in $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^i y^{n-i} = (x+y)^n$.

Then $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^i (1-x)^{n-i} = (x+1-x)^n \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^i (1-x)^{n-i} = 1$.

Hence, the theorem is proved.

Theorem 3. 2:
$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} (1-x)^i x^{n-i} = 1.$$

Proof. Let us substitute $y = 1 - x$ in $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} y^i x^{n-i} = (y + x)^n.$

Then $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} (1-x)^i x^{n-i} = (1-x+x)^n \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} (1-x)^i x^{n-i} = 1.$

Hence, the theorem is proved.

Corollary 3. 1:
$$\sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n-i} V_i^{n-i} 2^i = 1.$$

Corollary 3. 2:
$$\sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^i V_i^{n-i} 2^{n-i} = 1.$$

Corollary 3. 2:
$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^{n-2i} = \left(\frac{1}{x} + x\right)^n.$$

Corollary 3. 4:
$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^{2i-n} = \left(x + \frac{1}{x}\right)^n.$$

4. Conclusion

In this article, theorems and corollaries on binomial coefficients were constituted. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real world problems.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation and Calculus for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Identities and Expansions. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(7), 14648–01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss7pp14648-01i>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Application of Factorial and Binomial identities in Information, Cybersecurity and Machine Learning. *International Journal of Advanced Networking and Applications*, 14(1), 5258-5260. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53-v21>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2022) Combinatorial and Multinomial Coefficients and its Computing Techniques for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(8), 14713–01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss8pp14713-01i>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation of Multinomial and Factorial Theorems for Cryptography and Machine Learning. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks-v9>.

- [5] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation of Binomial, Factorial and Multinomial Theorems for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks-v11>.
- [6] Annamalai, C. (2022) Series and Summations on Binomial Coefficients of Optimized Combination. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(3), 14123-01e. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss3pp14123-01e>.
- [7] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorials and Integers for Applications in Computing and Cryptography. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.
- [8] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computing Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4168016>.
- [9] Annamalai, C. (2022) Annamalai's Binomial Identity and Theorem, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.
- [10] Annamalai, C. (2010) Applications of exponential decay and geometric series in effective medicine dosage. *Advances in Bioscience and Biotechnology*, 1(1), 51-54. <https://doi.org/10.4236/abb.2010.11008>.
- [11] Annamalai, C. (2017) Analysis and Modelling of Annamalai Computing Geometric Series and Summability. *Mathematical Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences*, 6(1), 11-15. <https://doi.org/10.15415/mjiss.2017.61002>.
- [12] Annamalai, C. (2017) Annamalai Computing Method for Formation of Geometric Series using in Science and Technology. *International Journal for Science and Advance Research In Technology*, 3(8), 187-289. <http://ijsart.com/Home/IssueDetail/17257>.
- [13] Annamalai, C. (2017) Computational modelling for the formation of geometric series using Annamalai computing method. *Jñānābha*, 47(2), 327-330. <https://zbmath.org/?q=an%3A1391.65005>.
- [14] Annamalai, C. (2018) Novel Computation of Algorithmic Geometric Series and Summability. *Journal of Algorithms and Computation*, 50(1), 151-153. <https://www.doi.org/10.22059/JAC.2018.68866>.
- [15] Annamalai, C. (2018) Computing for Development of A New Summability on Multiple Geometric Series. *International Journal of Mathematics, Game Theory and Algebra*, 27(4), 511-513.
- [16] Annamalai, C. (2020) Combinatorial Technique for Optimizing the combination. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 6(2), 0189-0192. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl6iss2pp0189-0192>.

- [17] Annamalai, C. (2018) Annamalai's Computing Model for Algorithmic Geometric Series and Its Mathematical Structures. *Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 3(1),1-6
<https://doi.org/10.11648/j.mcs.20180301.11>.
- [18] Annamalai, C. (2018) Algorithmic Computation of Annamalai's Geometric Series and Summability. *Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 3(5),100-101.
<https://doi.org/10.11648/j.mcs.20180305.11>.
- [19] Annamalai, C. (2019) Recursive Computations and Differential and Integral Equations for Summability of Binomial Coefficients with Combinatorial Expressions. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Mechanical and Materials Engineering*, 4(1), 6-10.
<https://ijsrmme.com/IJSRMME19362>.